

Photometric systems for Gaia's Broad Band Photometer (2)

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ABSTRACT. Two photometric systems for the Gaia broad-band photometer (BBP) are proposed, called 4B and 5B. System 4B consists of five trapezoidal filter bands covering the wavelength region 425–965 nm roughly equidistant in $\log \lambda$. System 5B is equivalent to 4B with the addition of two slots for a medium-band filter centered on 510 nm.

1 Assumptions

Telescope transmittance: Ag coating with six reflections is assumed.

Quantum efficiency: CCD-AF

Integration time per CCD crossing: 3.315 s (one slot) or 1.915 s (4 or 6 slots).

Filter transmittances: quasi-trapezoidal shape centred on λ_0 , defined by the convolution of four rectangular functions of width $\Delta\lambda$, $\delta\lambda$, w and w . The parameters are given in Table 1. The transmittance at the maximum is assumed to be 0.90.

2 Main parameters and response curves

The main parameters of the filters and photometric bands are given in Table 1. The 'sensitivity' $W\tau$ is defined as in GAIA-LL-045 ($W = \int R(\lambda)d\lambda$ being the integral of the response function).

The response functions are shown in Fig. 1.

Data file: BBP-4B-5B.txt

FIGURE 1: Response functions (i.e., total transmittance times quantum efficiency) for systems 4B and 5B. The solid curves are the response curves for the five broad bands B47, B55, B65, B76 and B89 (same for system 4B and 5B). The dashed curve around 510 nm is the response curve for the medium band M51. The Astro G band (i.e., telescope transmittance times quantum efficiency) is also shown as the wide, dotted curve.

TABLE 1: Main characteristics of the BBP systems 4B and 5B. λ_{lo} , λ_{hi} are the wavelengths at half-maximum filter transmittance; λ_0 is the central wavelength; $\Delta\lambda$ is the FWHM; $\delta\lambda$ is the edge width and w the rounding width; τ is the integration time per Astro FOV transit; $W\tau$ is the total sensitivity of the band (integrated response times integration time).

System	Band	Filter $\lambda_{lo}/\lambda_{hi}$	CCD type	λ_0 [nm]	$\Delta\lambda$ [nm]	$\delta\lambda$ [nm]	w [nm]	τ [s]	$W\tau$ [nm s]
4B	B47	425/510	CCD-AF	470	85	20	10	3.315	69
4B	B55	510/600	CCD-AF	555	90	20	10	1.915	98
4B	B65	600/700	CCD-AF	650	100	20	10	1.915	133
4B	B76	700/820	CCD-AF	760	120	20	10	1.915	141
4B	B89	820/965	CCD-AF	890	145	20	10	1.915	73
5B	B47	425/510	CCD-AF	470	85	20	10	3.315	69
5B	B55	510/600	CCD-AF	555	90	20	10	1.915	98
5B	B65	600/700	CCD-AF	650	100	20	10	1.915	133
5B	B76	700/820	CCD-AF	760	120	20	10	1.915	141
5B	B89	820/965	CCD-AF	890	145	20	10	1.915	73
5B	M51	495/525	CCD-AF	510	30	10	10	2×1.915	50